

*Climate and cultural based design and market valuable
technology solutions for Plus Energy Houses*

Vademecum to guide the designers through PEB climate and cultural design

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Executive summary

This Vade mecum for the design of Plus Energy Buildings (PEB) addresses all key topics to support designers, architects, and investors in working through the different steps of climate and cultural design. It collects the experience and results of the first direct application of a climate-cultural approach to building and system design, looks at the effectiveness and efficiency of some advanced technologies implementation and operation processes, suggests a checklist with the ambition of making the method used in H2020 Cultural-E project easily replicable by designers and other stakeholders in future PEB projects.

1 What is a Plus Energy Building?

Figure 1: Infographic of the PEB definition developed within the Cultural-E project

A Plus Energy Building is an energy-efficient building that produces more final energy than it uses via locally available renewable sources over a period of one year. Building uses include both building operation and user-related energy consumption. The positive balance shall be reached while ensuring the **lowest greenhouse gas emissions** and a **good dynamic matching** between load and generation, according to economic affordability and technical viability. The definition applies to all-electric buildings and the energy balance is based on **measured or predicted final energy** between load and generation.¹

The energy generation shall be performed by **renewable energy systems located within the building footprint** and can be extended to adjacent lots if there is a physical connection and direct control of renewable energy generation system relying on ownership of the buildings or lots, neighbourhood grid infrastructure and building management. Besides the plus energy balance verification, PEBs shall ensure an added value

- i) to the context by providing **building flexibility and easy access to e-mobility and**

¹ In case of new buildings electrification is an inevitable process. In case other renewable energy vectors are used in the building (i.e. biomass, biogas...), final energy balance shall be zero.

ii) to final users by providing accessible, comfortable and healthy indoor environments.²

² Source: <https://www.cultural-e.eu/peb-definition/>

2 The Cultural-E demonstration buildings in EU

2.1 The Norwegian demonstration building

The Norwegian demo is an almost a plus energy building used as an assisted living and welfare building. The building is part of the "Assisted living and welfare technology" program in Bærum municipality, where users can rent apartments. There are 12 apartments with one occupant per unit, and the building is managed round-the-clock by onsite staff. The building has an advanced BMS (Building Management System), giving the possibility of a high level of control.

The building is located just outside (11 km) Oslo city center in Bærum municipality. The climate there can be classified as subarctic, but due to proximity to the coast, the winters are not extremely cold, and summer temperatures are fair. The mean temperature in January is -3 °C and +18 °C in July. There are about 2400 sun hours a year, and precipitation is about 700 mm per year (snow in the winter and rain in the summer).

Figure 2: Site location of the Norwegian demo-case - Eiksveien 116

The area per apartment is about 60 m². The building has three floors, with apartments on the second and third floors. The staff areas are on the ground floor, consisting of offices, meeting rooms and restrooms. The common areas on the 1st and 2nd floor are common living rooms with a kitchen and a hallway. Outside, there are parking areas with EVs and E-bike charging possibilities.

Number of floors: 3 floors - 1st floor has staff offices, technical room and storage rooms.

Number of dwellings: 12 apartments – 6 on 2nd and 6 on 3rd floor, plus common areas on both floors.

Outdoors: Green space around the building and parking for bikes and cars (5 EV chargers).

Surface areas:

- Total Building 1350 m², building plot area 2705 m²
- 12 Apartments, 60 m² pr unit

Figure 3: Aerial view of the Norwegian demo-case building (courtesy of Bærum municipality)

Solution sets at building level:

- The building envelope and windows are highly insulated.
- The centralized electric boiler heats the floor and preheats domestic water in the whole building.
- Limited floor heating control (± 3 °C) in all rooms in apartments, common areas and offices.
- The boiler is connected to the 20kW heat pump.
- 3 geothermal wells provide energy to the heat pump.

- Advanced BMS (control of offices and common areas and metering in the apartments).
- PV panels on the roof (20kWp).
- Battery pack (7,2kWh).
- Centralized demand-controlled ventilation system (DCV) (common areas and offices).
- Charge points for wheelchairs in the hallway.
- 5 charge points for EVs outside.
- Motion detection light system in offices and common areas.
- An AMS (smart electric meters) registers all electric usage in offices and common areas.

Solution sets at apartment level:

- Automatic window blinds
- Balanced mechanical ventilation with heat recovery.
- Electric floor heating bathroom (thermostat);
- A private AMS registers electricity usage for each apartment.
- Energy meters for each apartment measure hot water usage and heating.

2.2 The Italian demonstration building

The Italian demonstration building is located in Castenaso, near Bologna (Italy), in a rural setting crossed by the river Idice and rich in parks and countryside. The location has a humid temperate climate with hot summers and relatively cold and wet winters. Average rainfall in the town ranges from 600 to 900 mm/y and is usually concentrated in spring and autumn. In winter, snowfalls can occur and are sometimes very abundant, with frequent night frosts. The modest windiness contributes to the formation of fog and mist and the permanence of high air pollution. Occasionally strong winds.

The demo includes two similar residential buildings with dwellings of different sizes, built by Abitcoop (a private cooperative, meaning they get an agreement for using public soil for 99 years) for selling. Each dwelling is equipped with LED lighting. Air movement is provided by VORTICE fans and is based on user activity levels. Buildings are equipped with photovoltaic panels on the roof; the system is divided into independent systems connected to each apartment's electrical system. Technical boxes on the balconies host each apartment's compact heat pump or HVAC/R unit and other technical services. A technical room hosts an inverter and batteries. Cabinets on each floor host the vertical distribution of electricity and water. Each dwelling hosts an HMS system, connecting to

room sensors and actuators, metering devices, HVAC and PV subsystems, VORTICE fans, user interfaces and cloudware.

- Pilot A: 3 floors, 6 dwellings
- Pilot B: 3 floors, 7 dwellings
- Surface area: approximately 75 m²/dwelling (60 -110 m²)
- Outdoor area: green area, parking

Figure 4: Illustration of the Italian demo-case building

2.3 The German demonstration building

The project is in Ostfildern near Stuttgart. At an altitude of approx. 410m above sea level, the climate is classified as warm and temperate. The annual average temperature in Ostfildern is around 10 ° C. The annual rainfall is around 877 mm.

With a mix of different floor plans and sizes, an attempt is made to appeal to a wide range of prospective tenants. The residential units will be realized as rental apartments. A large part of the lighting design will be pre-installed on site to ensure energy-efficient lighting. The kitchen electrical appliances (refrigerator, stove, cooker, oven, microwave, washing machine) are also made available to future tenants to ensure that highly efficient appliances are used.

- Number of floors: 4 Floors - A ground floor, two upper floors and an attic.
- Number of dwellings: 19 + 2 commercial units
- Surface areas:
- Residential units, 1st - 2nd floor and attic: 1470 m², average approx. 75 m²/apartment

- Commercial units, ground floor and 1st floor: 861 m²
- Underground: car parking, storage, technical cabinets: 1175 m²

Outdoors and common areas: green open spaces around the building, potentially partially green terraces.

Figure 5: Site location of the German demo-case building

Figure 6: Render of the German demo-case building

2.3.1 Solution set Attic

The solution set in two exemplary apartments in the penthouse (attic) consists of:

- Efficiency house 40 (EH40) envelope insulation standard
- PHP unit for heating, DHW and controlled mechanical ventilation (Ventive)
- Low temperature Under floor heating system
- Active window system (Eurofinestra) with integrated shading
- Highly efficient user appliances
- LED lighting system
- HMS and Cloud feedback system for user
- Connection to the buildings PV (80 kWp) and Battery system
- E-vehicle charger

2.3.2 Residential areas

The solution set of all other apartments consists of:

- Efficiency house 40 (EH40) envelope insulation standard
- Central air to water HP for heating and DHW
- Low temperature Under floor heating system
- Fresh water stations in the apartments for DHW
- Exhaust ventilation system
- Active window system (Eurofinestra) with integrated shading and trickle vents
- Highly efficient user appliances
- LED lighting system
- HMS and Cloud feedback system for user (Advanticsys)
- Connection to the buildings PV (80 kWp) and Battery system
- E-vehicle charger

2.3.3 Commercial area on the ground floor

The solution set consists of:

- Efficiency house 40 (EH40) envelope insulation standard
- Central air to water HP for heating
- Heating: Heated ceiling system
- Electric instantaneous water heaters for DHW
- Controlled ventilation system including heat recovery
- Ceiling fans (Vortice) for improvement of thermal comfort in summer

- LED lighting system
- HMS and Cloud feedback system for user (Advanticsys)
- Connection to the building PV (80 kWp) and Battery system
- E-vehicle charger

The heat pump can switch operation into cooling mode, which is used for a certain basic cooling in the commercial area by the heated ceiling system. In the residential areas, cooling mode is not available.

2.4 The French demonstration building

2.4.1 Roubaix demonstration case

This 4-storey residential building, initially built in 1984, was renovated in 2023-2024 with the objective of achieving Net Zero Energy (E=0) standard by applying the EnergieSprong approach. Innovative façade and roof prefabricated systems were used for the envelope refurbishment. Triple glazed windows and roller shutters were integrated. Heating and DHW are provided by collective heat pumps (one per four dwellings). 516 m² of PV panels are installed on the roof (117 kWp). Each apartment has also a double flow ventilation system with heat recovery (Passivhaus certified exchanger). The building is completely monitored. The people already lived in this building before the retrofit and it's possible to have a comparison point.

Figure 7: French demo-case building in Roubaix

2.4.2 Small-scale pilot in Tourcoing

A typical terraced house from the Northern France was deeply renovated in 2023-2024. Considering its architectural value, the façade remains intact, and insulation is internal. Some internal rooms are dedicated to the PHP unit that ensures heating, domestic hot water and ventilation. Air tightness should be at PassivHaus level. Considering the three stories, the stratification of the air in summer can lead to summer discomfort, and for this reason ceiling fans are installed in the bedrooms.

Figure 8: French small-scale pilot in Tourcoing (section and photo)

3 The Cultural-E checklist for Plus-Energy Buildings implementation

The Cultural-e project checklist provides a simple list of actions and requirements to guide the Plus Energy Buildings implementation. The checklist was divided into five main project phases: Design, Procurement, Construction, Commissioning and Monitoring and Post-Occupancy Evaluation (POE).

Checklist

Design Phase		
1		Implement bio-climatic design and innovative technologies in the early stages considering their maintenance, and life cycle.
2		Ensure early-stage collaboration between the design team (architects and engineers) to ensure the best possible integration between bio-climatic design and the building services technologies.
3		Design anticipating and prioritising user comfort and needs over most efficient use of technologies.
4		Engage at early-stage socio-technical professionals who can provide information on user needs and habits driven by local cultural and social-economic features. These boundaries conditions will inform the calibration of the building services technologies.
5		Assess energy consumption using energy simulations considering the local climatic conditions and the building archetype. ³
6		Integrate energy storage solutions like thermal storage and batteries
7		Design and size Heat, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) system considering passive solutions, users' habits, controllability at building scale and adaptability.
8		Design an integrated user-centred system controls and dashboard for data sharing with different access privileges.
9		Optimise Photovoltaic (PV) panel design considering load profile and price dynamics and battery system possible capacity. Architectural design considers the integration of PV panels in the roof and façade.

³ Cultural-E deliverable D4.7 "Factsheets reporting solution set description and metrics for each climate-cultural geo-cluster" <https://zenodo.org/records/8273531>

10		Integrate into design Electrical Vehicle charge points.
11		Improve communication strategy between the design team at different levels for a clear understanding of the new building services technologies and use.
12		Define the type of data collection: continuous monitoring or spot measurements.

Procurement Phase		
1		Adapt the contract or create a new type of contract that focus on collaboration and coordination between the design and construction team to deliver the building service system with all technologies integrated and fully functional.
2		Adopt a performance-based procurement that focus on the desire performance and end result rather than process and inputs.

Construction phase		
1		Training on-site construction workers on the new technologies to be implemented on site to reduce risks of delay and cost-raising potential.
2		Consider in large scale projects, the engagement of 'intermediary actors' to bridge, and a lean construction management ensuring achievement of the goals and schedule.

Commissioning phase		
1		Adapt the commissioning contract or create a new type of commissioning contract that focus on collaboration and coordination between the commissioning teams to deliver the building service system with all technologies integrated and fully functional.
2		Provide information on the maintenance of the new technologies and system for a better installation and follow up.
3		Engage an independent commissioner to ensure the correct installation and functioning as per design.

4	Plan the commission of large-scale projects in phases. Implement and complete the commission process in few units and replicate the process for the other units.
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Monitoring and Post-Occupancy Evaluation (POE)	
1	Include specifications on communication protocols, sensors, and signals in the monitoring system architecture.
2	Implement a cloud-based system to integrate the technologies and monitoring information.
3	Collect data on indoor environmental quality parameters such as temperature, relative humidity, CO2 levels, and pollutants.
4	Monitor parameters via continuous monitoring or spot measurements.
5	Maximize self-consumption by adopting predictive control strategies for energy storage management to mitigate the mismatch between energy consumption and production
6	Gather building user feedback through surveys, focus groups, semi-structured interviews, etc.
7	Plan feedback and collection of monitoring data at several points in the year in different seasonal conditions.
8	Providing information to building users for better use of the building system to ensure a healthy and comfortable indoor environment with minimal energy use. The information format should be adapted according to the local conditions and circumstances and could be printed or online home guides and training in person or online training, how-to-do videos, etc.

4 Conclusions

Early attention to bioclimatic, passive design, and innovative technologies is essential, as is knowing the surrounding infrastructure (e.g., mobility, data, energy, social), and possible connections. A particular focus should be given to properly integrating these technologies with the pre-existing conditions (if any).

It is highly recommended to take a 'Swiss knife' approach to the skills and competencies involved throughout all phases of the building process. This means engaging a wide variety of professionals, including architects, engineers, designers, socio-technical experts, contractors, and, of course, the occupants. This holistic approach should be applied at all stages, starting from the initial design phase and extending through to post-occupancy evaluation.

Effective monitoring combined with comprehensive Post-Occupant Evaluation (POE) offers valuable insights into the actual performance of Plus Energy Buildings (PEBs) and user interaction with the technologies. Future studies should focus on creating a clear and seamless connection between the monitored data and user feedback. This approach will ensure a deeper understanding of how occupants engage with the building systems in their homes, enabling more effective optimisation of both energy performance and user experience.

The checklist provides an easy and simple tool for guiding Plus Energy implementation. This ensures that every element is carefully addressed and implemented, resulting in a more successful and sustainable building outcome.

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